

Leveraging Technology to Transform Healthcare and Enhance Surgical Ward Efficiency in a Leading African Teaching Hospital

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Abstract

Context of the study: Surgical wards were critical to hospital operations, often serving as the backbone of inpatient care. However, inefficiencies in resource utilization, prolonged patient stays, and high bed occupancy rates significantly strained healthcare systems, particularly in resource-limited settings like Ghana. Despite their importance, comprehensive evaluations of ward performance that integrated both quantitative metrics and qualitative insights remained limited. Leveraging ten years of data (over 290,000 records) from Korle-Bu Teaching Hospital (KBTH), this study addressed a pressing need to evaluate and enhance surgical ward efficiency. By adopting the WHO's People-Centered Approach to Health Systems (PATH) Framework, it sought to bridge the gap between data-driven findings and patient-centered care, providing actionable strategies to optimize resource allocation and improve outcomes.

Research Objectives: This study aimed to evaluate the operational efficiency of surgical wards at KBTH, Ghana. Using the WHO's PATH Framework, the study sought to analyze key performance indicators such as Bed Occupancy Rate (BOR), Average Length of Stay (ALOS), Bed Turnover Rate (BTR), Turnover Interval (TOI), and Mortality Rate (MR) while integrating staff and patient perspectives to optimize resource allocation and improve patient-centered care.

Research Methodology Adopted: A 10-year retrospective, observational study spanning 2014–2023 with supplementary qualitative insights drawn from operational and clinical reports to contextualize the findings. Quantitative data from ward service activity records across eight surgical wards were analyzed retrospectively to identify trends and performance gaps using metrics such as admissions, discharges, deaths, etc. Using IBM SPSS Statistics 29.0, the study employed Pearson correlation, trend analysis, and Kruskal Wallis tests to identify significant differences. The analysis focused on five general surgical subspecialty disciplines within eight wards.

Key Findings and Practical Implications: Statistical analysis demonstrated significant differences between wards ($p < 0.001$) in bed availability, BTR, MR, BOR, TOI, TOR, and admission/discharge rates, with strong positive correlations between BTR and admission rates ($r = 0.749$ to 0.948) and discharge rates ($r = 0.904$ to 0.969). ALOS negatively correlated with admission rates ($r = -0.260$ to -0.575) and BTR ($r = -0.523$ to -0.698), while BOR showed strong positive correlations with admission rates ($r = 0.638$ to 0.890) and BTR ($r = 0.680$ to 0.901). Over the decade, ALOS decreased from 8.49 ± 1.23 days to 6.27 ± 1.1 days, while BTR increased from 1.9 ± 0.53 to 3.32 ± 1.09 . TOI decreased from 9.02 ± 5.29 days to 3.83 ± 2.55 days. Mortality rates peaked in 2021 ($7.59 \pm 6.73\%$) before stabilizing at $4.91 \pm 2.47\%$ in 2023. Qualitative analysis revealed that national cancer awareness campaigns and improved bed bureau coordination significantly influenced patient flow, while enhanced medical officer availability and better post-surgical monitoring contributed to mortality rate management. The general performance showed improved operational efficiency from 2014 to 2023, with shortened ALOS, improved BTR, and reduced TOI, though BOR remained below WHO-

recommended levels (75-85%). Ward efficiency practically can be achieved by implementing targeted bed management protocols including real-time tracking to achieve the WHO-recommended BOR of 75-85%. Standardize successful practices from SW2 and SW3 across all wards while monitoring quality metrics and optimizing transfer rates. Ensuring a reduced malfunction of beds and lastly investigating high mortality rates while reducing TOI to meet the “1-3” day standard.

Conclusion: This study established the essential role of adopting advanced software tools in managing and analysing extensive hospital service data to provide actionable and practical interventions to optimize surgical ward operations. While bed turnover and occupancy rates have improved, challenges such as resource constraints, malfunctioning beds, and external factors persist. Reducing turnover intervals, strengthening discharge protocols, and enhancing early intervention strategies can further improve outcomes.

Keywords: Surgical Ward, Efficiency, Resource Utilization, PATH Framework, Technology

Introduction

The digital transformation of healthcare adopts technologies like telemedicine, electronic health records, electronic health diagnostic wearables, research applications, and mobile health applications to monitor and therefore improve healthcare delivery to enhance patient outcomes and increase access to healthcare services. Digital health solutions have the potential to reduce health inequalities and increase well-being by changing how care and health services are provided (1). Digital interventions are essential or play a vital role in assessing hospital performance for the sake of improving healthcare delivery (2). Hospital performance assessment is critical to ensure that healthcare delivery is carried out optimally. Aside from the other avenues to assess the performance indicators such as Average Length of Stay (ALOS), Bed Occupancy Rate (BOR), Bed Turnover Rate (BTR), Bed Turnover Interval (TOI) and Morality Rate (MR) play an essential role in marking the operational performance leading to better patients outcomes and also the effective use of hospital resources (3, 4). These indicators are vital as it is evidence-based information that not only provides insights into healthcare quality but further improves hospital performance and also ensures continuous quality improvement. These hospital key indicators or metrics are evaluated with conventional standard benchmarks to promote effective resource utilization and better healthcare delivery. According to NHS (5) Bosque-Mercader and Siciliani (6) BOR which assesses the percentage amount of beds that are occupied within any given time is most efficient within 75% to 85%. (7, 8, 9). It is referenced that exceeding this threshold may signal safety and efficiency risk (5) and underutilization of resources when the metric falls below the threshold (9).

According to the OECD (10), ALOS marks the efficiency of healthcare delivery by measuring the average days a patient spends in the hospital before discharged. ALOS should be shorter as it marks efficient patient management and reduced healthcare delivery costs. However longer ALOS are linked to high readmission rates and premature discharges (10). The benchmark for this metric varies across several countries and as well as case conditions, however, a general standard or benchmark is between 5 to 6 days. Thus, a study indicated that for patients classified in lower risk classes (I–III), the target duration of hospitalization was set at 5 days, while higher risk classes (IV–V) had a target of 7 days. This suggests that a stay of around 5 to 6 days is often considered optimal for certain conditions (11). The other key metrics such as BTR, which measures the number of patients per bed in a given period (12), and TOI, which captures the time a bed remains vacant between discharges and new admissions, provide the inpatient workflows as well a better resource optimization (12, 13). A shorter TOI thus between 1-3 days and a higher BTR is ideal as they signal efficient use of hospital beds (12, 14). In guaranteeing that these hospital bed metrics facilitate actionable enhancements in hospital efficiency and patient care, this study follows the guidelines set by the World Health Organization.

This utilizes the World Health Organization's PATH (People-Centered Approach to Health Systems) Framework. The PATH framework stresses people-centered care, accountability, team-based care, and system strengthening, making it a relevant model for addressing gaps in hospital performance evaluation and resource optimization. This study's metrics closely align with the PATH Framework, focusing on key aspects of healthcare delivery. Patient-centered care is measured through admission rate, discharge rate, transfer rate, and death rate. Accountability is ensured through BOR, BTR, and average daily census, optimizing resource utilization and patient flow. ALOS measures patient-centered care, indicating the quality of patient management and outcomes, while turn-interval is crucial for achieving efficient patient flow and minimizing turnover intervals. Furthermore, MR contributes to health system strengthening by identifying structural inefficiencies and informing strategic investments in hospital resources and policies.

Despite advancements in healthcare quality monitoring, the application of these metrics in low- and middle-income countries, including Ghana, remains largely underexplored (15). Existing studies in Ghana have primarily concentrated on patient satisfaction (16) and quality dimensions (14), often neglecting the essential role of performance metrics in decision-making. Moreover, there is a lack of data on the neurosurgical disease burden and capacity in many African countries (17), as well as limited evidence on how these capacity indicators vary across specialized wards (18) or impact outcomes such as mortality.

Technology and data have been used in the past and current to transform several institutions across the world. Solutions like Fujitsu's Surgical Capacity Optimization (SCO) provide insights gleaned from data to enable perioperative teams to develop optimal operating room schedules, identify new surgery times, and enhance utilization rates (19). Further, data envelopment analysis assists nursing managers in optimizing nursing manpower and nursing performance allocation, ultimately improving nursing service efficiency (20). However, limited and poor-quality health data present a significant challenge to implementing digital health solutions in Africa (Musa et al., 2023). Despite advancements in healthcare quality monitoring, the application of these metrics in low- and middle-income countries, according to Escribano-Ferrer, Cluzeau (15) Ghana remains highly underexplored. Existing studies in Ghana have primarily focused only on patient satisfaction (16, 21) and quality dimensions (14), often ignoring the critical role of performance metrics in decision-making.

To address this gap, this study appraises ten years of hospital data from Korle-Bu Teaching Hospital using the PATH framework as a guiding model for analysis and interpretation, specifically focusing on the general surgery wards. By analyzing BOR, ALOS, BTR, TOI, and their correlations, this study aims to identify trends, disparities, and predictors of operational efficiency. Incorporating the PATH framework allows the study to align findings with actionable strategies for people-centered, accountable, and efficient care delivery.

Methodology

Settings

Korle Bu Teaching Hospital (KBTH) in Accra, Ghana Established in 1923, is a leading tertiary healthcare in the nation and further is known to be renowned for its excellence in Africa. It is known for the wide clinical range of specialized services it offers. The services include cardiology, oncology, neurosurgery, pediatric care etc. The Surgery Department, KBTH provides specialized services across different specialties. Especially for the general surgery wards: the 2nd floor houses the Breast Care and Chemotherapy Suite, the 3rd floor is dedicated to Hepato-Biliary care, the 4th floor focuses on Colorectal surgery, and the 5th floor specializes in Endocrine surgery, including Goitre and Hernia treatments. The department has a bed capacity of 223 serving an average patient volume of 80,000 per year (22).

Data Source

The data was a ten-year data obtained from the Surgical Dept. Medical Records outfit of the Korle Bu Teaching Hospital's database. The data contained daily bed utilization records for each specialty ward through 10 years spanning from 2014-2023. The data set originally included variables such as patient census, number of admissions, discharges, deaths, and trans ins and outs. Based on this dataset, several performance bed metrics or performance indicators were derived and these included Admission Rates (AR), Discharge Rates (DR), Transfer in Rates (TIR), Transfer Out Rates ALOS, BOR, MR, TOI, and BTR.

Study Design & Framework

The study mainly was a retrospective observational study conducted over ten years spanning from 2014-2023 to evaluate key performance metrics in the General Surgical specialties (wards) at the Korle-Bu Teaching Hospital. It included a comprehensive analysis of over 200,000 bed (ward) service activity records from the eight surgical wards, focusing on General Surgery specialty wards (SW2 - SW5) and their corresponding bed utilization indicators.

This study adopted the World Health Organization's PATH Framework to evaluate the operational performance of these surgical wards of the Korle-Bu Teaching Hospital. This framework was adopted as it emphasizes the importance of people-centered care, accountability, team-based collaboration, and health system strengthening, making it particularly relevant for this analysis. It provides a structured method or approach to ascertaining the performance of the surgical wards.

Inclusion Criteria

Data from the Surgical wards between 2014–2023.

Exclusion Criteria

Pediatric specialty ward Data
 VIP-specific ward Data

Table 1: Data Variables

Variables	Unit of Measurement	Definition
Ward Service Activities		
Admission	Counts	Number of admissions per day for each ward
Available bed days	Count in days	Available beds throughout the review period.
Beds	Counts	Number of beds for each ward
Date	Date	Date of each of the variable activities
Death	Counts	Number of death recorded per day for each ward
Discharge	Counts	Number of clinical discharges per day for each ward
Patient days	Count in days	Cumulative total of bed state
Patients	Counts	Number of patients in bed per day for each ward
Trans in	Counts	Number of patients transferred from other wards
Trans Out	Counts	Number of patients transferred from the hosting ward
Ward	String	Name of the ward
Metric Variables Definition		
ALOS	Day counts	Average length of stay before discharge
BOR	Percentage	Percentage of beds occupied per period
TOI	Days counts	Average vacancy days before the next patient admission

BTR	Percentage	Average no, of patients per bed during a specified period
MR	Percentage	Measures the number of deaths per period

Definition from IFHIMA (23) and Formula referenced from Mehrtak, Yusefzadeh (24)

Data Collection Procedure

By way of technology, we collected and extracted the data from the surgical wards from the repository of data accumulated in a Design Microsoft Excel template covering the period from 2014 to 2023. The wards included were The Neuro-Surgical Ward (SW1); the General Specialist Wards, which comprised breast care, thyroid, hepatobiliary, and colorectal specialties (SW2, 3, 4, and 5); the Genito-Urinary Specialist Ward (Ward G); the VIP Ward (SW6); and the Paediatrics Ward (PS Ward). The study focused on only 5 wards i.e., Wards 2 to 5. The daily nature of data collected included patient admissions, discharges, deaths, and transfers (both in and out). Further bed utilization metrics/indicators such as AR, DR, TIR, TOR, MR, BOR, and BTR were derived or calculated. In addition to collecting quantitative data, operational interviews with ward managers and clinical reports from all wards were reviewed. These reports provided insights into ward-specific practices.

Data Quality and Handling of Missing Values

Data reliability and validity was ensure by, several data quality control measures we put in place as checks. Initially, all data extracted were subjected to multiple sessions of verification by ward in charges/ managers approving these data and another session to validate if data was the true reflection. The process involved cross-checking daily entries for consistency, correcting obvious typographical errors, and removing duplicate records if any.

Missing data at the first level were identified through the data validation checks at the data generation point and after data extraction excel functions built into the excel template was used to check for any missing data values. Data imputation was used to handle the missing values using linear interpolation where appropriate. Insights from clinical reports and interviews with ward managers were used to triangulate and interpret anomalies in the data trends, such as sudden spikes or drops in indicators like MR or BOR.

Data Analysis Plan

The collected data were reviewed for completeness and consistency to ensure that only records meeting the inclusion criteria were analyzed. Summary statistics, including mean, standard deviation, median, and ranges, were calculated to compare key ward service activities and performance metrics across the surgical wards. The data analysis plan was done strategically following the WHO PATH Framework. This was to enable the flow of understanding and coherence of the study. The PATH framework measures the patient flow (P), the Activity(A), Time(T) and the Hospital Stay(H) to evaluate the efficiency by way of performance of the surgical specialties. In this regard, the plan is seen in Table 2.

Table 2: Aligning Metrics with the PATH Framework

Patient Flow (P)	Definition	Analysis
1. AR	Total admissions per year/total bed capacity	Comparison of indicators across wards to identify differences. Pearson Correlation and Trend analysis over time
2. DR	Total discharges per year/total bed capacity	
3. Transfer Rate	Total transfers per year/total admissions	
4. Death Rate	Total deaths per year/total admissions	

Activity (A)		
1. BOR	Bed days occupied/Available bed days x 100	Pearson Correlation and Trend analysis over time
2. BTR	Total admissions/total available beds	
3. Average Daily Census	Total patients present in the ward at midnight/total available beds	
Time (T)		
1. ALOS	Total patient days/total discharges	
2. TOI	The time between patient discharge and the next admission	
Hospital Stay (H)		
1. MR	Total deaths/total admissions x 100	

Statistical Analysis

The data analysis involved descriptive statistics thus mean, standard deviation (SD), median, and interquartile range (IQR) to summarize patient flow and hospital performance indicators across surgical wards. The Kruskal-Wallis test was used to compare differences in bed metrics among the wards. Trend analysis was conducted to examine changes in ALOS, BOR, BTR, TOI, and MR over ten years. Pearson correlation analysis was used to assess relationships between key hospital metrics AR, DR, TIR, TOR, BTR, and BOR, while ALOS and TOI. Comparative ward analysis was performed to evaluate variations in hospital performance across SW2, SW3, SW4, and SW5. The qualitative interviews were transcribed, and relevant extracts from reports were incorporated and analyzed using content analysis.

Results

Characteristics of Ward Activities

Tables 3 and 4 present a summary of patient flow in the various surgical specialty wards. Across all these wards, the patient volume, admissions, discharges, and transfer activities displayed moderate variability, while bed capacity remained relatively stable within the same ten-year period of assessment. SW2 recorded the highest mean patient count (552.98 ± 101.83), while SW5 had the lowest (503.50 ± 110.57), with admissions following a similar pattern, ranging from 58.80 ± 13.79 in SW5 to 69.73 ± 14.45 in SW3. In Table 4, Discharge rates were highest in SW3 (61.61 ± 13.44) and lowest in SW5 (53.9 ± 13.21), aligning with transfer-in and transfer-out trends, where SW3 had the highest movement (T'in: 11.10 ± 6.27 , T'out: 11.82 ± 7.1). MRs were relatively low, with SW5 reporting the lowest mean (3.08 ± 2.68) and SW3 the highest (5.45 ± 2.8). Despite minor variations, median bed availability ranged from 32 to 38 across all wards.

Table 3: Summary of Patient Flow across Surgical Wards

Ward	Patients	Admission	T' In
SW2			
Mean	552.98 ± 101.83	67.81 ± 14.54	9.30 ± 15.38
Median	573(490.2-629.8)	68(58-76)	9(5-12)
SW3			
Mean	550.33 ± 106.44	69.73 ± 14.45	11.10 ± 6.27
Median	551(477.3-614.3)	70(61.25-80)	10(6-14)
SW4			
Mean	529.91 ± 105.26	64.32 ± 12.3	9.65 ± 6.12

Median	51950(454.2-597)	64(55.25-73)	9(4-13)
SW5			
Mean	5.82 ± 110.57	58.80 ± 13.79	8.81 ± 6.13
Median	503.50(440-561.75)	58(50-68)	7(4-12)

Table 4: Summary of Patient Flow Across Surgical Wards Cont...

Ward	Discharge	T' Out	Deaths	Beds
SW2				
Mean	59.98 ±11.3	10 ±5.7	5 ±3.76	30.8 ±1.7
Median	60(53.35-67)	9(6-13)	4(3-6)	32(29-32)
SW3				
Mean	61.61 ±13.44	11.82 ±7.1	5.45 ±2.8	34.3 ±6.5
Median	63(53.3-71)	10.5(7-16)	5(3.25-7)	38(32-38)
SW4				
Mean	56.95 ±11.96	9.80 ± 6.3	4.64 ± 2.85	35.30 ±3.9
Median	56(49-66)	9(5-14.8)	4(2.25-6)	38(32-38)
SW5				
Mean	53.9 ± 13.21	9.56 ±6.8	3.08 ±2.68	34.5 ± 4.7
Median	53.50(44-63)	8(4-15)	2(1-4)	38(28-38)

In Table 5 significant differences were found across the surgical wards in bed availability, BTR, MR, BOR, TOI, TOR, discharge rate, and admission rate ($p < 0.001$), with SW2 consistently showing higher patient admission and bed utilization, while ALOS and TIR did not differ significantly.

Table 5: Comparison of Key Hospital Performance Indicators Across Surgical Wards

Metrics	Ward	Mean Rank	X ² (df)	P-Value
Beds	SW2	139.70	97.49(3)	0.00
	SW3	278.90		
	SW4	281.30		
	SW5	262.10		
ALOS	SW2	243.92	6.12 (3)	0.11
	SW3	214.80		
	SW4	246.15		
	SW5	257.14		
BTR	SW2	296.25	40.4(3)	0.00
	SW3	259.71		
	SW4	212.65		
	SW5	193.39		
MR	SW2	253.27	32.77(3)	0.00
	SW3	275.98		
	SW4	252.75		
	SW5	180.00		
BOR	SW2	304.46	40.87(3)	0.00
	SW3	242.43		
	SW4	214.35		
	SW5	200.76		
TOI	SW2	173.53	50.72(3)	0.00
	SW3	226.55		

	SW4	271.52		
	SW5	290.40		
TIR	SW2	251.14	10.02(3)	0.18
	SW3	266.92		
	SW4	229.31		
	SW5	214.63		
TOR	SW2	256.39	44.05(3)	0.00
	SW3	266.35		
	SW4	222.06		
	SW5	217.20		
DR	SW2	303.30	44.05(3)	0.00
	SW3	253.50		
	SW4	208.75		
	SW5	196.45		
AR	SW2	303.34	51.6(3)	0.00
	SW3	261.48		
	SW4	212.18		
	SW5	185.00		

Chi-Square = X², Degree of freedom = Degree of Freedom

Year	ALOS (Days)	BTR (Pt/bed)	Mortality (%)	BOR (%)	TOI (Days)
2014					
Mean	8.49 ±1.23	1.9 ±0.53	5.03 ± 2.82	47.09 ±14.4	9.02 ±5.29
Median	8.5[8.50 - 9.18]	1.8[3.00 - 7.00]	5[5.0-7.0]	50 [40-60]	7.80 [5.05 - 11.53]
2015					
Mean	8.35 ±1.59	1.92 ±0.58	6.32 ±5.09	45.21 ±13.1	9.68 ±6.10
Median	8.4[7.43 - 8.98]	2[3.00 - 8.00]	6.50[3.0- 8.0]	40.00 [10-57.5]	8.00[5.48 - 11.70]
2016					
Mean	8.2 ±2.21	1.64 ±0.41	6.42 ±4.79	41.88 ± 11.61	11.16 ±5.18
Median	8.85[7.50 - 10.0]	1.7[4.00 - 8.00]	5[5.0-8.0]	40[30 - 50]	10.05[7.40 - 13.00]
2017					
Mean	8.2 ±2.21	1.76 ±0.38	6.4 ± 4.3	40.42 ±8.75	10.28 ±2.88
Median	7.90[6.6-8.5]	1.8[3.25 - 9.00]	6.0 [4.0-9.0]	40.0[32.5 - 47.5]	9.60[8.13 - 11.95]
2018					
Mean	7.24 ±1.18	1.93 ±0.39	5.9 ±3.45	40 ±10.72	9.50 ± 2.92
Median	7.1[6.30 - 8]	1.9[4.00 - 7.75]	6.00[3.5-7.5]	40[30 - 47.5]	9.70[7.80 - 11.38]
2019					
Mean	7.54 ±1.25	2.05 ±0.41	6.17 ± 3.0	44.80 ±10.52	8.18 ±2.88
Median	7.3[6.45 - 8.08]	2[4.00 - 8.00]	6.00[4.0-8.0]	40[40- 50]	8.10[6.13 - 10.03]
2020					
Mean	7.47 ±1.35	1.96 ±0.54	6.94 ±3.56	41.05 ±12.59	10.21 ±7.01
Median	7.35[6.40 - 8.0]	2[16.0-2.00]	6.50[4.0-9.0]	40[30 - 50]	8.65[6.20 - 12.20]
2021					
Mean	6.55 ±1.05	2.87 ±0.49	7.59 ±6.73	55.21 ±9.23	4.62 ±1.72
Median	6.3[5.70 - 7.35]	2.85[3.00 - 9.00]	6.0[3.0-9.0]	60[50 - 60]	4.20[3.60 - 5.40]
2022					
Mean	6.37 ±0.9	3.3 ±0.35	6.32 ± 3.96	68.41 ± 10.73	3.02 ±1.21

Median	6.37[5.70 - 6.82]	3.22[3.40 - 8.33]	6.27[3.9-8.3]	68.96[59.66 - 75.84]	2.90[2.17 - 3.96]
2023					
Mean	6.27 ±1.1	3.32 ±1.09	4.91±2.47	66.32 ±19.11	3.83 ±2.55
Median	5.91[5.51 - 7.12]	2.89[2.99 - 6.67]	5.16[2.9-6.6]	60.84[52.41 - 77.50]	3.74[1.73 - 5.58]

In Table 6 within the ten years, it is noticed that the ALOS showed a study declining trend, from a peak of 8.49 ± 1.23 days in 2014 to 6.27 ± 1.1 days in 2023. Simultaneously, as ALOS was noticed to decline, BTR rather steadily increased, from 1.9 ± 0.53 in 2014 to a peak of 3.32 ± 1.09 in 2023. (BOR) initially declined, from 47.09% in 2014 to a low of 40% in 2018–2020, but sharply increased post-pandemic, peaking at 68.41% in 2022 before slightly declining to 66.32% in 2023. Meanwhile, Turnover Interval (TOI) exhibited a decreasing pattern over the period, dropping from 9.02 ± 5.29 days in 2014 to 3.83 ± 2.55 days in 2023, with a sharp decline after 2020, reflecting increased hospital efficiency and bed turnover.

MRs fluctuated over the years, peaking at $7.59 \pm 6.73\%$ in 2021 before declining to $4.91 \pm 2.47\%$ in 2023. Before the pandemic year 2020, MRs remained between 5.03% and 6.94%, but post-pandemic (2020, 6.9%), a spike was observed in 2021 (7.59%) before stabilizing in subsequent years (2022 and 2023). The most notable improvements occurred after 2020 (Table 6).

Table 6: Trends in Hospital Performance Indicators/Metrics (2014–2023)

Comparative Analysis of Hospital Performance Indicators Across Wards

A comparative analysis of hospital performance indicators across four wards (SW2, SW3, SW4, and SW5) is shown in Table 7. It presents the variations in patient ALOS, BTRs, MRs, BORs, and TOIS. ALOS varied across wards, with SW5 recording the highest mean ALOS at 7.90 ± 2.18 days, followed by SW4 (7.63 ± 1.69 days) and SW2 (7.52 ± 1.47 days). SW3 had the shortest ALOS, averaging 7.15 ± 1.25 days. BTR was highest in SW3 (2.49 ± 1.09), closely followed by SW2 (2.46 ± 0.55). Conversely, SW5 had the lowest BTR (2.02 ± 0.79). SW3 recorded the highest mortality at $6.79 \pm 3.07\%$ while SW5 had the lowest ($4.89 \pm 4.57\%$). Comparably, BOR was highest in SW2 ($55.08 \pm 12.47\%$) with SW3 having a slightly lower BOR ($51.36 \pm 20.21\%$), while SW4 ($45.86 \pm 13.84\%$) and SW5 ($43.86 \pm 13.47\%$) recorded the lowest BOR (Table 7).

The TOI, which measures the time beds remain unoccupied between patient admissions, showed a decreasing trend from SW5 to SW2. SW5 recorded the longest TOI at 9.88 ± 6.14 days, followed by SW4 (8.67 ± 4.31 days). Meanwhile, SW2 had the shortest TOI (5.80 ± 3.03 days), followed by SW3 (7.46 ± 5.27 days). Generally, SW2 exhibited high bed utilization and patient flow efficiency but also had a relatively high MR. SW3 maintained the highest BTR but recorded the highest MR, while SW5 had the longest TOI yet the lowest MR

Table 7: Comparative Analysis of Hospital Performance Indicators Across Wards

Ward	ALOS	BTR	Mortality (%)	BOR	TOI
SW2					
Mean (SD)	7.52 ± 1.47	2.46 ± 0.55	6.72 ± 4.98	55.08 ± 12.47	5.80 ± 3.03
Median (IQR)	7.30(6.60- 8.28)	2.5(2 - 2.9)	6.00(4- 8)	60.00(50-60)	5.06(3.6- 6.9)
SW3					
Mean (SD)	7.15 ± 1.25	2.49 ± 1.09	6.79 ± 3.07	51.36 ± 20.21	7.46 ± 5.27
Median (IQR)	7.10(6.20- 8.00)	2.10(1.8- 3)	6.75(4.8- 8.4)	40.0(40.0- 60.0)	7.40(3.8- 9.6)
SW4					

Mean (SD)	7.63 ±1.69	2.09 ±0.65	6.40 ±3.78	45.86 ±13.84	8.67 ±4.31
Median (IQR)	7.50(6.30- 8.38)	2.00(1.6- 2.5)	6.00(3.7- 9)	40.0(31.8- 57)	8.67(5.33- 11)
SW5					
Mean (SD)	7.90 ±2.18	2.02 ±0.79	4.89 ±4.57	43.86 ±13.47	9.88 ±6.14
Median (IQR)	7.50(6.10- 9.18)	1.80(1.5- 2.6)	4.00(2- 6.8)	40.0(30-54.4)	9.50(5- 11.98)

Interquartile Range = IQR, Standard Deviation =SD

Correlation Among Metrics

The analysis in Table 8 revealed strong positive correlations between BTR and both AR ($r = 0.749$ to 0.948) and DR ($r = 0.904$ to 0.969). ALOS was negatively correlated with AR ($r = -0.260$ to -0.575) and BTR ($r = -0.523$ to -0.698). Similarly, BOR shows strong positive correlations with AR ($r = 0.638$ to 0.890), BTR ($r = 0.680$ to 0.901), and DR ($r = 0.610$ to 0.896).

TIR and TOR rates are strongly correlated with each other ($r = 0.819$ to 0.919) and show moderate to strong positive associations with BTR and Admission Rate. Conversely, TOI exhibits strong negative correlations with Admission Rate ($r = -0.705$ to -0.806), BTR ($r = -0.814$ to -0.878), and BOR ($r = -0.811$ to -0.860). Finally, MRs show weak or insignificant correlations with most operational metrics.

Table 8: Relationship Between Performance Metrics by Ward

Ward	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
SW2									
1. AR	1								
2. ALOS	-	1							
3. BTR	.749**	-	1						
4. DR	.731**	-	.904**	1					
5. MR	-.195*	-.189*	0.115	-0.118	1				
6. BOR	.638**	.196*	.680**	.610**	-0.080	1			
7. TIR	.400**	-0.166	.655**	.415**	0.015	.568**	1		
8. TOR	.544**	-.192*	.683**	.389**	-0.040	.553**	.819**	1	
9. TOI	-	0.179	-	-	0.003	-	-	-	1
SW3									
1. AR	1								
2. ALOS	-	1							
3. BTR	.948**	-	1						
4. DR	.930**	-	.969**	1					
5. MR	-0.116	-0.127	-0.060	-0.179	1				
6. BOR	.890**	-	.901**	.896**	-0.171	1			
7. TIR	.783**	-	.879**	.778**	0.009	.778**	1		
8. TOR	.733**	-	.807**	.649**	0.059	.685**	.899**	1	
9. TOI	-	.450**	-	-	0.124	-	-	-	1
SW4									
1. AR	1								
2. ALOS	-	1							
3. BTR	.853**	-	1						
4. DR	.861**	-	.945**	1					
5. MR	-0.074	-0.134	0.056	-0.080	1				

6. BOR	.800**	0.015	.790**	.788**	-0.018	1			
7. TIR	.522**	-	.743**	.568**	-0.037	.556**	1		
8. TOR	.566**	-	.780**	.570**	-0.031	.525**	.888**	1	
9. TOI	-	.338**	-	-	-0.011	-	-	-	1
SW5									
1. AR	1								
2. ALOS	-	1							
3. BTR	.917**	-	1						
4. DR	.913**	-	.967**	1					
5. MR	-.220*	0.018	-0.057	-0.121	1				
6. BOR	.759**	-0.130	.757**	.745**	0.001	1			
7. TIR	.757**	-	.828**	.709**	-0.162	.613**	1		
8. TOR	.766**	-	.850**	.713**	-.187*	.599**	.919**	1	
9. TOI	-	.434**	-	-	0.047	-	-	-	1

Significance = “**“

Overall Relationship between Performance Metrics

The 10-year correlation analysis of hospital performance metrics is shown in Figure 1. Higher AR (A_RATE) were strongly correlated with increased BTR, DR (D_RATE), and BOR (OCC Rate). Similarly, BTR was strongly associated with D_RATE and BOR. ALOS shows a moderate to strong negative correlation with A_RATE and BTR. Likewise, TOI is negatively correlated with A_RATE, BTR, and BOR. TIR (Tin_RATE) and TOR (Tout_RATE) rates demonstrate a strong positive correlation. Additionally, moderate positive associations between transfer rates and both BTR and BOR indicate that efficient patient movement supports overall hospital performance. Lastly, MR (M_RATE) exhibits weak or inconsistent correlations with operational efficiency metrics, implying that improvements in hospital efficiency do not necessarily influence mortality outcomes.

Figure 1: Overall Correlation Matrix of Performance Metrics

The Trend of Ward-by-Ward Bed Metrics

SW2 has consistently maintained a higher occupancy rate compared to the other wards, with a relatively stable trend over the years. MR remained steady as well, except for notable increases in 2015 and 2021 (figure 2). Both the ALOS and TOI showed a steady decline (figure 3). Similarly, the BTR remained largely stable, though a slight overall increase was observed, albeit not statistically significant (figure 4).

The ALOS for SW3 remained consistently stable (figure 3), ranging between a minimum of six days and a maximum of eight days (Table 5). During this period, the number of free bed days before the next admission (TOI) generally decreased (figure 3) to implicate shortened TOI, although some years experienced sharp upward trends thus largely in 2015 to 2016 and 2020 (figure 3). Further, the general decrease in TOI indicates an increased patient admissions and therefore high bed turnover rate (Figure 4). Additionally, the occupancy rate (figure 1) has been steadily rising, reaching full bed occupancy in 2023 (Figure 1). Despite these changes, mortality remained stable at 6.7% throughout the years (Figure 1). The increasing occupancy rate trend in Figure 2 is further reflected in Figure 4, which shows an increasing BTR and is also confirmed by the strong positive significant correlation ($r=.896$ $p<.001$) (table 6).

From 2014 to 2023, ALOS for SW4 has been steadily decreasing and similarly, the TOI has also declined (Figure 3) confirmed by the weak positive significant correlation ($r=.338$ $p<.001$), this means that after a patient's discharge, the next admission occurs within a shorter period. Additionally, the BTR has shown a steady increase from 2014 to 2022, before stabilizing in 2023 (figure 4). Similarly, the BOR has been rising since 2014 and plateaued between 2022 and 2023 (figure 2). Mortality trends have remained relatively stable, with occasional fluctuations, but overall, there was a general decline from 2014 to 2023.

Over the years for Ward 5, the occupancy rate steadily increased. Despite this, mortality remained stable throughout the period. The TOI showed a general decline, meaning beds were being occupied more quickly after discharge. However, there were occasional spikes, particularly largely between 2015–2016 and again in 2020. The ALOS consistently decreased meanwhile, the BTR remained stable from 2014 to 2019 but rose sharply from 2020 to 2023, suggesting an increase in patient admissions and overall hospital activity.

Figure 2: Trend of BOR and MR across wards from 2014-2023

Figure 3: Trend of ALOS and TOI across wards from 2014-2023

Figure 4: Trend Analysis of BTR Across Wards from 2014 to 2023

Qualitative Results

Qualitative interviews and extracts from reports were analyzed and summarized into the PATH framework as seen in Table 7

Table 7: Summary of Qualitative Interviews

PATH Component	Metric	Contributing Factors	Impact %	Key Influences
Patient Flow (P)	Admissions	External referrals Walk-in cases Post-COVID surge Cancer awareness campaigns	15%	Increased referrals post-COVID Direct ward re-admissions for post-discharge complications Breast Cancer Awareness Month impact
	Discharges	Treatment completion - Recovery status - Discharge protocols	10%	Timely discharge processing after successful surgeries Post-operative recovery progress Availability of follow-up care
	Transfers	Cross-ward movements Bed Bureau allocation - Specialty requirements	8%	Bed Bureau Unit coordination Inter-ward patient distribution Specialty care needs
	Death Rate	Case complexity Medical officer availability Critical care capability	7%	Medical officers are permanently available as against the previous lack of shortage. Better post-surgical monitoring Enhanced emergency response
Activity (A)	BOR	Available functional beds - Patient volume Length of stay	20%	Reduction in functional beds Increased complex cases Resource availability
	Bed Turnover Rate	Discharge efficiency - Admission coordination - Bed preparation time	12%	Immediate bed reassignment Consumables availability Staffing levels
	Average Daily Census	Ward capacity – Staff availability – Resource management	8%	Reduced bed numbers Staffing adequacy Supply chain efficiency
Time (T)	ALOS	Case complexity Surgery scheduling Post-op complications	12%	Neuropatient extended stays Surgical timing – Complication management
	Turn-Over Interval	Bed Bureau efficiency cleaning protocols Staff coordination	3%	Minimal bed idle time Quick turnover process Efficient bed allocation by the bureau
Hospital Stay (H)	MR	Clinical expertise Patient monitoring Emergency response	5%	Permanent medical officers for Improved monitoring Better intervention timing

Discussion

Patient Flow (P)

The surgical wards demonstrated varying patterns of bed utilization and patient movement over the study period. While the WHO recommends an optimal BOR of 75-85%, most wards operated below this target possibility due to several factors such as the malfunction proportion of beds, and resource

constraints, and external factors such as pandemics, strike actions. This is consistent with the National Health Service of England claims that malfunctioning beds and lack of necessary repairs limit the total bed availability for more admissions (25) and also with the National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (26). The breast specialty ward (SW2) consistently maintained the highest occupancy rates due to an increasing number of referral cases from different hospitals due to limited facilities that see breast conditions (27) and this was seen particularly after COVID-19, as well as the influence of breast cancer awareness initiatives as it leads to changing the health seeking behavior of individuals impacting admissions (28). The hepatobiliary ward (SW3) experienced significant occupancy changes, reaching full capacity by 2023. This was driven by the admission of other surgical specialty patients with chronic conditions, which required extended hospital stays, ultimately increasing the ALOS and bed BOR. The bed bureau unit also served as a major factor in regulating the admission (29) of patients to wards with low occupancy rates. They account for the metric variability across the surgical wards. The external factors have been a significant factor in affecting the patient flows in several hospitals. There have been several strike actions that also involve healthcare professionals and these have resulted in a reduction in hospitalizations leading to poor patient outcomes (30, 31) these factors may explain the sharp increases in TOI or as seen in the decline in admission rates observed across the wards, particularly between 2014 and 2017, as TOI is consistently and significantly negatively correlated with admission rates. The initiation of breast cancer awareness, and colorectal cancer awareness, which aim to increase public awareness, etc, are all attracted external impacts on hospitalization (32, 33). Generally, while patient flow efficiency has improved across the surgical wards, challenges remain in optimizing bed utilization and transfer protocols. SW3, in particular, faces sustained pressure due to the admission of long-stay patients and unscheduled direct admissions, while SW2's bed capacity is influenced by seasonal and referral-based factors. Strengthening resource allocation, including consumables and bed management strategies, will be critical in addressing these challenges and ensuring sustained efficiency across the wards.

Activity (A)

In the efficiency and utilization of hospital resources, particularly bed management and patient flow within wards the BTR and BOR were observed to have shown significant improvement over the years across the wards. Vukey, Ntow-Kummi (34) claim High BTR suggests that a high admission rate, showing improved hospital productivity, and decreasing average cost per admission. The observed monthly BTR increased from 1.9 patients per bed (22.8 per bed yearly) in 2014 to 3.32 patients per bed (39.84 per bed yearly) in 2023. This suggests a decrease in TOI, as BTR was consistently and significantly negatively correlated with TOI ($r = -0.80$ to -0.86 , $p = .000$) across all wards, exceeding the international standard of 1–3 TOI or a benchmark BTR of 17 patients per bed yearly as suggested in the systematic review by Parvaresh and Esfandnia (35). The performance was quite high as compared to the 22 patients per bed per year in teaching hospitals in Southeast Nigeria reported by Aloh, Onwujekwe (36). The Qualitative insights reveal that the bed bureau unit plays a crucial role in optimizing bed occupancy by quickly assigning patients to available beds, even when staff may not be on duty. This practice minimizes idle bedtime and supports the increased BTR.

Time (T)

The ALOS across the surgical wards decreased generally from 8.5 days to 6.2 days although there was no significant difference ($p > .05$) in ALOS among the wards. This however signaled improvements in patient management and discharge efficiency as compared with the national standard of 5 days recommended by the Ghana Health Service (GHS) days per admission" (37) and lower than most developed countries within the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) countries which has ALOS within 5-8 days (10, 38). It is also essential to mention that ALOS can vary significantly depending on the specific country, healthcare system, and disease condition (39) and is also affected by the severity of the medical condition (40). This is seen in the qualitative insight of this

study when for instance, complications arising from chronic cases or complex surgeries can prolong hospital stays and affect overall ALOS metrics, despite these challenges the enablers in the ALOS reduction were also attributed to the posting of permanent medical officers, the provision of adequate staffing, improvements in coordination among care teams facilitated quicker identification and management of post-operative complications, thereby promoting timely discharges. While these positive trends are encouraging, continued efforts are needed to further reduce turnover intervals and refine discharge processes across all surgical wards. Addressing the specific needs of specialized cases and ensuring efficient resource allocation will be crucial in achieving even greater efficiencies in patient flow and optimizing ALOS.

Hospital Stay (H)

MRs have emerged as a key area for improvement across the surgical wards, with figures ranging from 4.89% to 6.79%, exceeding the typical benchmark of 2-4% for surgical units (41). The MRs were significantly different across the wards but were very independent or mostly not correlated ($p > 0.05$) with any of the metrics. These rates could be influenced by the rampant referrals of cases from the lower facilities as indicated by the qualitative insights and the late reporting of medical conditions such as cancers (42). Peak MRs were observed in 2015 and 2021, periods likely influenced by external factors such as the COVID-19 pandemic, which may have exacerbated underlying health issues among patients (30, 31, 43). In SW3, the MR remained stable at 6.7%, while SW5 reported the lowest MR at 4.89%, despite its longer ALOS. This suggests that other factors, such as patient case complexity, play a significant role in determining outcomes. For example, SW3 has seen an increase in admissions for complex neurosurgical cases since 2020, which could contribute to higher MRs despite improved management practices. Qualitative findings indicate that the presence of permanent medical officers in the wards has positively impacted patient outcomes by facilitating timely interventions for post-surgical complications. However, the weak correlation between MRs and operational efficiency metrics underscores the importance of considering additional variables, such as the severity of patient conditions and the nature of surgical procedures, when evaluating overall performance.

Practical Implications and Recommendations

To optimize resources, targeted strategies should be implemented to ensure all beds are consistently functional to have adequate BOR toward the WHO-recommended 75–85% range, particularly in lower-occupancy wards. Real-time bed tracking strategies should be developed as well as standard bed management protocols.

Additionally, the efficient practices from high-performing wards (SW2 and SW3) should be standardized across all units. Enhancing patient flow requires maintaining the positive BTR trend while ensuring quality metrics are monitored, as well as addressing variations in transfer rates to optimize patient movement between wards.

For quality improvement, factors that led to the high MRs compared to standard benchmarks should be investigated. Lastly, improving operational efficiency should focus on reducing TOI across all wards to meet the “1-3” day standard.

Conclusion

Key performance indicators showed positive trends in length of stay and bed turnover rates over the study period. However, several metrics remained below international benchmarks, particularly bed occupancy rates which fell short of WHO recommendations and were influenced by critical factors such as non-functional beds and staffing, while turnover intervals exceeded standard ranges despite improvements. The strong and significant correlations between the operational metrics signaled opportunities for systemic improvements, particularly in patient flow management. The variation in performance across surgical wards, from high bed utilization to lower MRs in different wards,

suggested potential benefits from standardizing best practices while maintaining specialty-specific considerations.

Moving forward, targeted strategies should focus on optimizing bed utilization, reducing turnover intervals, and investigating factors contributing to above-benchmark MRs. These improvements, guided by the PATH framework findings, would enhance operational efficiency while maintaining quality care standards at Korle-Bu Teaching Hospital, with potential applications for similar healthcare facilities in Ghana.

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